

ICSU World Data System Annual Report 2014–15

Prepared by the WDS International Programme Office

Trusted Data Services for Global Science

Credits:

p1: Artwork, Museum of Old and New Art, Tasmania,
Australia by Data.Tron; Colorized transmission electron micrograph
showing H1N1 influenza virus particles by NIAID; Pre-Winter Storm, Australia by
NASA; Honey Bee on Mountain Mint by John Baker; Scientists prepare for planet Mars on the
Mojave by woodleywonderworks; Hump Back Whale, South Island, New Zealand by Gemma Louise Lowe;
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ICSU World Data System
Annual Report 2014–15

Prepared by the WDS International Programme Office

WDS Strategic Targets 2014–2018

1. Make trusted data services an integral part of international collaborative scientific research
2. Nurture active disciplinary and multidisciplinary scientific data services communities
3. Improve the funding environment
4. Improve the trust in and quality of open Scientific Data Services
5. Position ICSU-WDS as the premium global multidisciplinary network for quality-assessed scientific research data

Introduction

The mission of the ICSU World Data System (ICSU-WDS) is to promote long-term stewardship of, and universal and equitable access to, quality-assured scientific data and data services, products, and information across a range of disciplines in the natural and social sciences, and the humanities. ICSU-WDS aims to facilitate scientific research under the International Council for Science's (ICSU's) umbrella by coordinating and supporting trusted scientific data services for the provision, use, and preservation of relevant datasets, while strengthening their links with the research community. WDS was established by ICSU in 2009, building on the recognized legacy of its World Data Centres and Federation of Astronomical and Geophysical data analysis Services.

2014–2015 in Brief

November 2014 saw ICSU-WDS and the Committee on Data for Science and Technology hold their first joint biennial conference, SciDataCon 2014, in New Delhi, India. With the theme Data Sharing and Integration for Global Sustainability, the conference represented a milestone in discussions on the role of scientific data to address global change and global sustainability issues.

A major highlight of the conference was presentation of the inaugural WDS Stewardship Awards to Drs Robert Redmon and Xiaogang Ma. This yearly award showcases exceptional contributions to the improvement of scientific data stewardship by early career researchers through their engagement with the community, academic achievements, and innovations.

Prior to conference, over 70 people participated in the 2014 WDS Members' Forum. In the Scientific and Plenary Sessions of this open business meeting, WDS Members supported a set of Bylaws for managing the daily affairs of WDS, and agreed to produce a public report of their activities every two years.

Sandy Harrison was appointed to the WDS Scientific Committee (WDS-SC) in May 2014. Sandy was a guest at the 10th WDS-SC Meeting, during which the SC refined the WDS Strategic and Implementation Plans before formally publishing these documents in June. The Strategic Plan 2014–2018 outlines five targets identified for ICSU-WDS to achieve its objectives, and operates in unison with the evolving Implementation Plan, which lists activities for realizing the targets.

As WDS coverage broadens across new scientific domains, the WDS-SC also re-examined the 'full and open access' concept at its 10th Meeting, and on the basis of this, began to revise the WDS Data Policy at its 11th and 12th Meetings. The endorsement of open access principles at the 31st ICSU General Assembly is of particular importance to WDS in this process.

Message from the Executive Director

The 2014–2015 period was intense, rich, and very productive for the ICSU World Data System and its International Programme Office (IPO). As you will discover reading the pages of this Annual Report, we actively supported the work of our Scientific Committee (SC) and Working Groups, tirelessly travelled the world on long-haul, economy-class flights to present and represent the interests of ICSU-WDS at international meetings, and to work with fellow international experts on several initiatives relevant to the WDS endeavour.

I particularly enjoyed contributing to one of these initiatives—the e-Infrastructure and Data Management Coordinated Research Action—as a member of its Steering Committee. This project was launched by the Belmont Forum, bringing together the world’s major funding agencies of global environmental change research. The objectives of the first phase (2 years) of this project were to gather and coordinate input from relevant experts and the wider data community to ultimately deliver recommendations aimed primarily at research funders. These recommendations should provide an actionable roadmap to implement sustainable e-infrastructures and data management practices and better support research. After three meetings during the period covered by this Report—including those hosted by ICSU-WDS in Paris and Tokyo—the Steering Committee is on target to deliver its Community Strategy and Implementation Plan in mid-2015, with the hope of having an impact and influence on future Belmont Forum projects and funding streams.

The focus of this activity addresses directly two of WDS’ Strategic Targets for 2014–2018: Make trusted data services an integral part of international collaborative scientific research; and Improve the funding environment for scientific data services. Science is under public scrutiny and ensuring its reliability requires building trust in the underlying data infrastructure. WDS Member Organizations provide reliable data infrastructures and trusted services to support research in a wide range of disciplines. Therefore, developing and maintaining a healthy research environment depends heavily on their sustainability and adequate funding.

Mustapha Mokrane, Executive Director

Message from the Chair

WDS has gained global visibility and a reach into domains that were beyond the boundaries of its predecessors. Its 2014–2018 Strategic Plan reflects this expanded scope. Certainly, the timing has been serendipitous: all of society is not only talking about data but also contemplating the opportunities opened by data publication. Our tagline 'Trusted Data Services for Global Science' reveals the pivotal role that WDS Members play in this arena.

WDS is not alone, of course, and our collaboration with CODATA is more effective than ever, SciDataCon 2014 but one example. Every year, new Memoranda of Understanding are being signed with cooperating entities such as DataCite, and the interest/working groups and data conferences of global organizations such as the Research Data Alliance become even more alluring and better attended. WDS Members are active participants in building this future, and our commitment to the critical role of the next generation of scientists is represented by the yearly WDS Data Stewardship Award.

A metric of maturity for a volunteer organization like WDS is that all the founding SC members have completed their terms of service. A parallel metric of success is that finding replacements is not hard. In fact, the most difficult part is choosing from the long list of excellent candidates. So I salute my colleagues on the WDS-SC who started with me in 2009, and served one term (Baoping Yan, Dave Clark, Luiz Horta, Michael Zgurovsky, Pierre Cilliers, Takashi Watanabe); those who agreed to serve a second term (Françoise Genova, Lesley Rickards, Michael Diepenbroek, Ruth Neilan); and those who joined at that time (Ariel Troisi, Claudia Emerson, Guoqing Li,, Jane Hunter, Kim Finney, Ryosuke Shibasaki, Sandy Harrison, Vasily Kopylov, Wim Hugo), some of whom will serve a second term under the chairmanship of Sandy Harrison. Success would have eluded us without your dedication and enthusiasm. To you all, my deepest gratitude!

To that list, I must add the ICSU-support offered over the years by Carthage Smith, Deliang Chen, Howard Moore, Maureen Brennan, Orhan Altan, Rohini Rao, and Tish Bahmani-Fard, and the support of NICT through Yasuhiro Murayama. Finally, since 2012, the indefatigable IPO team of Mustapha Mokrane, Rorie Edmunds, and Yuko Nikaido, under the wise guidance of Takashi Watanabe, has brought us along a stable trajectory that I am confident can be sustained in future years. And to all you WDS Regular, Network, Partner, and Associate Members, thank you for your participation, and for making WDS what it is today.

Chairing the WDS-SC for the past six years has been one of the most rewarding endeavours of my career. I shall miss it.

Bernard Minster, Chair WDS-SC

Activities in Priority Areas

WDS Data Stewardship Awards 2013 & 2014

SciDataCon 2014: International Conference on Data Sharing
and Integration for Global Sustainability

WDS Working Groups

Links with Partners

WDS Data Stewardship Awards 2013 & 2014

Dr Robert Redmon and Dr Xiaogang Ma were presented with the WDS Data Stewardship Awards for 2013 and 2014 at the SciDataCon 2014 conference. The WDS Data Stewardship Award highlights exceptional contributions to the improvement of scientific data stewardship by early career researchers through their engagement with the community, academic achievements, and innovations.

Dr Robert Redmon is an outstanding early-career researcher at the US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) who has demonstrated an amazing capacity for, and dedication to, scientific data stewardship. Within the World Data Service for Geophysics [WDS Regular Member], Dr Redmon is responsible for stewarding, and delivering to the international research community, the space environmental datasets obtained from NOAA's Polar-orbiting and Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite systems. By leveraging his background in computers, engineering, and science—as well as his clear understanding of customer needs—Dr Redmon has developed crucial capabilities to support the scientific community and to facilitate the transition of research to operations. Dr Redmon has continually demonstrated innovation in space weather applications. He was primarily responsible for the successful transition of the Ovation auroral model into NOAA National Weather Service operations.

Dr Xiaogang Ma is a geoinformatics and data science researcher. His PhD research at ITC, University of Twente was closely related to OneGeology—a global data exchange initiative—while more recently, he has worked on provenance representation and capture of data in scientific workflows at Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute. Dr Ma is a member of the International Association for Mathematical Geosciences (founder and first president of ITC student chapter, 2010; councillor candidate, 2011), American Geophysical Union (data science session organizer at Fall Meetings, 2013 & 2014), Federation of Earth Science Information Partners [WDS Partner Member] (Semantic Web and Data Stewardship clusters), and Commission for the Management and Application of Geoscience Information (Geoscience Terminology Working Group). Dr Ma also coordinated the GeoData 2014 workshop and the 2014 Deep Carbon Observatory Data Science Day symposium, and organized a data provenance session at the Association of American Geographers 2014 Annual Meeting.

SciDataCon 2014: International Conference on Data Sharing and Integration for Global Sustainability

SciDataCon2014 took place on 2–5 November in New Delhi, India; hosted by the Indian National Science Academy. This international conference was co-organized by the World Data System and the Committee on Data for Science and Technology [WDS Associate Member] (CODATA)—the two bodies under the International Council for Science (ICSU) with responsibilities for data policy and stewardship—and was the first time that the two organizations have joined forces to convene an international meeting designed to confront data issues.

International Scientific Organizations Support Data Sharing for Sustainability

The Press Release issued after the conference is [available on our website](#).

With the theme *Data Sharing and Integration for Global Sustainability*, the conference was motivated by the conviction that the most significant research challenges—and in particular, the pressing issues relating to global sustainability in the face of ongoing natural and human-induced changes to the planetary system—cannot be properly addressed without paying attention to issues relating to data such as policy frameworks; quality and interoperability; long-term stewardship; and the skills, technologies, and infrastructures required by increasingly data-intensive science.

By bringing together the CODATA and WDS memberships and the wider scientific and policy communities to seek answers to questions, including:

- What policies, standards, skills, and technologies are required to ensure that valuable data are not only preserved for the long-term but also findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable?
- How do we combine diverse datasets from different scientific disciplines?
- How can we maximize the use of datasets to answer new questions?

SciDataCon2014 addressed a range of important issues connected with global change and global sustainability. Moreover, it called for an urgent and persistent response by international science to the huge data challenges presented, and hence was an important first step in increasing the role of scientific data in transforming our world and moving towards greater equity and sustainability.

Selected Papers from International Polar Data Forum Published

A special issue of the CODATA Data Science Journal entitled '*Highlights of the 2013 International Forum on 'Polar Data Activities in Global Data Systems'*' was published on 30 October 2014 to coincide with the first anniversary of the ICSU-WDS co-hosted International Polar Data Forum.

The issue contains selected papers from the Forum, and alongside the Communiqué released directly after the meeting, reinforces the message that core data services for the polar region must be sustained and enhanced into the future.

WDS Working Groups

Publishing Data

The WDS Working Group (WG) on Publishing Data was started in late 2012 with the aims of identifying and defining best practices for data publication, as well as testing its implementation by involving core stakeholders. The WDS concept addresses essential problems and practical issues such that publication of research data can become part of the scholarly record. Because the involved issues are interlinked, the following four WGs were eventually established.

Bibliometrics – Investigates and develops solutions that enable proper analysis of data content and citations. Its activities address several different levels: Organizational, Technical, Methodological, and Financial.

Cost Recovery – Supplies cost estimates and elaborates a business model to compensate for additional costs of publishing data in an open access environment. Its work builds on: current cost models, funding policies related to cost recovery, existing business models, the position and policies of stakeholders in the publishing process, and the outcomes of the Workflows WG.

Services – Investigates content requirements for data services and academic publishers, and addresses the problem of limited interoperability among these and the tools for bibliometric analysis. Its focus is on the conception and implementation of a one-for-all cross-referencing service; building on existing processes, workflows, and solutions between parties in the data publication landscape.

Workflows – Analyzes existing and emerging workflows and standards for data publishing, including deposit and citation, and provides reference models and implementations for application in new workflows.

These WGs have been placed under one coordination umbrella Interest Group (IG). Hence, interaction and exchange of results between WGs is monitored and guided by a common structure that ensures contribution by all interested parties.

Progress in 2014–2015

The early months of fiscal year 2014 (FY2014) saw the Data Publishing WGs endorsed by the Research Data Alliance [WDS Associate Member] (RDA), with their Case Statements accepted by the RDA Technical Advisory Board (TAB) in May 2014. However, the Cost Recovery WG was seen as being outside the scope of RDA, and instead became an Interest Group. In contrast, ICSU-WDS decided that the deliverables of this WG are too important to the overall goals of the umbrella IG to exclude them, and thus the WG is continuing as a WDS-only exercise. The work then began of trying to achieve the deliverables of the WGs, especially those feasible for completion by the RDA Fourth and Fifth Plenaries.

The Bibliometrics WG conducted a survey in September 2014 aimed at investigating what is currently used by researchers/funders/repository managers to quantify the impact of data, and what they would like to use for this. Preliminary and more comprehensive results of the survey were presented at the RDA Fourth and Fifth Plenaries. At the close of FY2014, analyses of the survey results were being used to create a report addressing several use cases.

With the help of volunteers, the Cost Recovery WG conducted a series of hour-long structured interviews (following a script) with data repositories over the telephone/online. It then collected and summarized its findings, and is in the process of writing a report on these findings to share with repositories.

The Services WGs was particularly fast moving in FY2014, and has already developed

- A set of ratified guiding principles for the crosslinking service between data and articles.
- User scenarios (with contributions from related initiatives) for researchers; research institutes, data centres, publishers, service providers, and so on; and contributors.
- A schema including metadata and an information model.
- A test corpus of article-data linked organizations.
- Phase 1 of a technical prototype/demonstrator.

The number of groups (DataCite, CrossRef, OpenAIRE, ORCID, Thomson Reuters, etc.) that are part of this initiative is proof that the WDS cross-referencing service concept is not only valid but also valuable to the community, and it is extremely likely to be realized. The next steps for the WG are to complete phases 2 and 3 of the prototype, and optimize the information model. It will also seek to formalize a relationship with DataCite and CrossRef, who are working together to accelerate the adoption of Digital Object Identifiers for data publication and citation.

The Workflows WG presented the initial results of an analysis of existing and emerging workflows and standards for various data publishing stakeholders at the RDA Fourth Plenary, looking at a number of categories including permanent identifier assignment, peer review, curation, discoverability, formats, standards, and so on. From this analysis, the WG has been able to create generic repository and publishers workflows as the starting point for reference models. In March 2015, the WG was moving to the implementation phase, developing use cases for workflows, with the goal of selecting key organizations in which components of the reference models can be tested for suitability such that they can ultimately be applied in new workflows. A report will be produced by the WG, summarising the results of the workflows investigation.

Several funding proposals on behalf of the WGs were submitted to the European Union side of the Horizon

2020 project to (1) link ORCID, DataCite, data centres, and publishers, and thus address the underlying service infrastructure for identifiers, and (2) build the core components needed to realize the objectives of the WGs.

The umbrella IG's breakout session at the RDA Fourth Plenary was highly successful, attaining an audience of greater than one-quarter of the total participants. This group is increasing not only in number but also in importance. Under ICSU-WDS, the two-year renewal deadline for the IG (and thus the WGs) was reached in November 2014. The WDS Scientific Committee (WDS-SC) decided that in contrast to the 18-month timescale under RDA, the WGs will most likely continue for at least the next 5 years.

Data Publishing Webinars

On 13 May 2014, the WDS International Programme Office (WDS-IPO) co-organized a Webinar with the International Association of Scientific, Technical and Medical Publishers [WDS Associate Member] (STM). This Webinar was arranged primarily for STM members and their colleagues, and consisted of a series of talks by the Co-chairs of the Data Publishing IG and four WGs.

A similar Webinar was then organized for WDS Members and other interested data services on 2 October 2014, with attendees updated on the current activities of the Publishing Data initiative.

WDS Webinars

Recorded webinars
are [available on our website](#).

Knowledge Network

The Knowledge Network (KN) is a Web-based, interlinked repository of relationships between the actors and entities that make up the research landscape: people, institutions, projects, and so on. ICSU-WDS has a stated objective to establish an aggregation of WDS Members' metadata holdings (the Metadata Catalogue; MC) so that the extent of data and services offered are discoverable through a single interface. However, ICSU-WDS would like to go further by creating a broad KN in which additional information sources are used to supplement the MC by means of Linked Open Data repositories. Such information sources include the WDS-IPO's existing membership database, as well as the Global Registry of Trusted Digital Repositories and Services (GR) that ICSU-WDS is taking a leadership role in the establishment of, in collaboration with DataCite and re3data. Through its KN, ICSU-WDS will thus enhance the usefulness of its MC; improving the ability of researchers, funding agencies, and data service managers to fully extract the value of the information contained in WDS Members' metadata.

Progress in 2014–2015

The three initiatives of a GR, MC, and overarching KN, progressed in separate but parallel streams in FY2014.

The focus for the KN was on completing the prototype development phase, and implementing an operational system. The National Institute of Information and Communications Technology extended an offer to fund the latter, and much of 2014 was concerned with determining the resources required to build a pilot implementation of the KN using standards and specifications derived from the prototype model. In early 2015, Online Computer Library Center, Inc. (OCLC) also offered to play a role in realizing the operational KN, and the close of FY2014 saw the WG learning about OCLC's work and

determining its contribution to the KN. The WG hopes to have the pilot KN completed in the near future such that it can be used to give a common understanding of what is meant by 'knowledge network' in the WDS context.

The survey conducted by the WDS-IPO in 2013, showed that greater than 80% of WDS Regular and Network Members can potentially be included in the MC. The major task of the WG in FY2014 was to liaise with those Members in order to answer specific questions on their metadata services, as well as on their metadata granularity. This communication exercise was still ongoing as FY2014 drew to a close.

Work on the GR was continued through the WG contributing to discussions about the process for integrating re3data's registry under DataCite; explaining the goals of the GR so that they can be included to the largest possible extent. ICSU-WDS also offered its views on potential collaborations among the organizations at DataCite's Annual Meeting (25–26 August; Vandœuvre-lès-Nancy), and the WG is hoping to reinforce these connections at the 2015 Annual Meeting.

Chinese WDS Members to Develop Common Clearing House

Representatives of Chinese WDS Regular Members (WDS China) met in June 2014 at the World Data Centre for Renewable Resources and Environment in Beijing to discuss building a strong contribution from WDS China towards the MC. Chinese data services will work in unison to agree on a standard protocol to provide a dynamically updated metadata service in English. Moreover, WDS China is leading a project to use brokering technology to consolidate the unique data holdings generated by Chinese research teams into a common clearing house as a single channel for ICSU-WDS to harvest its metadata.

Certification

Data sharing enables reuse of data and ultimately makes science more transparent. To ensure the quality and usability of shared data and to provide long-term preservation and access, sustainable data services are key components of scientific infrastructure. However, it is vital to guarantee the trustworthiness of a service to perform these functions, and certification by an appropriate authority is fundamental in promoting confidence in shared data resources.

The Data Seal of Approval (DSA) and ICSU-WDS are two examples of organizations that have set up basic certification mechanisms for trusted repositories and data services. Their catalogues of criteria and review procedures are based on the same principles of openness, and of balancing the simplicity and robustness of the work involved. By reconciling the certification mechanisms of DSA and ICSU-WDS, this will simplify the array of certification options, and show the value to be gained from a certification procedure requiring relatively low investment of time and effort.

Progress in 2014–2015

The WG was formally endorsed by the RDA TAB in late May 2014. However, it held its first official telecon in April 2014 to commence with its initial task of generating a high-level mapping between the WDS and DSA catalogues of criteria. The WG began by concentrating on the repository function that is common to the catalogues, whilst being careful not to forget the specific distinctions of the organizations. The different vocabularies used by DSA and ICSU-WDS were considered especially important, as well as differences in the DSA framework where sections are answered on behalf of the data producer and user.

The WG had developed mappings in both directions by the end of June 2014. ICSU-WDS and DSA then had internal

discussions on the mappings before providing feedback to the joint WG in order to identify issues that needed to be addressed. Work thus continued on the Common Catalogue of Requirements such that Version 1.0—with agreed language, and a glossary based on that of the Open Archival Information System reference model—was available by the end of the calendar year.

Guidance text for each of the Common Requirements was finalized in February 2015, and the WG then turned to the procedural parts of the DSA and WDS certification processes, to explore how well these map to each another.

The WG held successful breakout sessions at the RDA Fourth and Fifth Plenaries, where it presented its work to the larger community in order to drive the work forwards. The WG additionally organized a session at SciDataCon 2014, where its discussions were progressed even further by engaging with a new and diverse audience.

The deadline for the WG's renewal under ICSU-WDS was reached at the 11th Meeting of the WDS-SC in November 2014. The WG's 18-month timescale under RDA will finish in November 2015, and the SC consequently agreed to extend the term of the WG until that time, and examine its renewal at the 13th WDS-SC Meeting in autumn 2015.

Links with Partners

ICSU Committee on Data for Science and Technology

In addition to SciDataCon 2014, the World Data System and the Committee on Data for Science and Technology (CODATA) furthered their close collaboration by WDS co-sponsoring the CODATA-convened workshop *Big Data for International Scientific Programmes: Challenges and Opportunities*. Held on 8–9 June 2014 in Beijing, China, this workshop was targeted at shedding light on the potential role of Big Data in international and interdisciplinary research activities, including for ICSU-sponsored programmes such as Future Earth and Integrated Research on Disaster Risk (IRDR), as well as other international initiatives. As a first, practical step towards focussing attention on this area, the workshop participants and sponsoring organizations agreed on a Statement of Recommendations and Actions that calls on CODATA to establish a Working Group (WG) to address the recognized Big Data issues for international research programmes, and WDS to solve associated data stewardship and curation matters.

Research Data Alliance

ICSU-WDS had a strong presence at both the Fourth (22–24 September 2014, Amsterdam, Netherlands) and Fifth (9–11 March 2015, San Diego, USA) Plenary Meetings of the Research Data Alliance (RDA), organizing a number of coordinated breakout sessions for the joint RDA–WDS Interest Groups (IGs) and WGs on Data Publication and Repository Certification. ICSU-WDS also held a Science Stream on Knowledge Networks at the Fourth Plenary.

The Fifth RDA Plenary commenced immediately after the 12th Meeting of the WDS Scientific Committee. During the Plenary, RDA celebrated its third year as an international organization by highlighting the outputs from its initial WGs—including those jointly under ICSU-WDS—and its attempts to ensure lasting impact in the research data sharing community through adoption by other organizations. In this regard, the RDA–WDS WGs are proceeding well with their work and are planning to have their deliverables ready by the Sixth RDA Plenary in September 2015.

CODATA, RDA, & WDS Announce Partnership

The Research Data Alliance and ICSU's Committee on Data for Science and Technology and World Data System have signed Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) outlining their collaboration.

The three organizations have different but complementary foci and strengths, and the MoUs clarify their respective strengths and enable the new Partnership to accomplish more; to advance data practices and science faster and further, and thus increase the benefit of research data for society.

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk

WDS joined the delegation from the International Council for Science (ICSU), who—as part of its mandate in co-sponsoring the IRDR programme—organized the Science and Technology Major Group at the Third UN World Conference on Disaster Risk Reduction (14–18 March; Sendai, Japan). This Group was successful in retaining the prominent references to science, and the data that underpin it, in the new 2015–2030 Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction, which was under negotiation at the conference. In particular, the Group’s official statement delivered by the IRDR Chair acknowledged the strong call in the Framework for science—and the availability of scientific data—to support the understanding of disaster risk and to promote risk-informed decisions and risk-sensitive planning from local to global levels.

International Council for Scientific and Technical Information

ICSU-WDS strengthened its position in the area of communication of scientific and technical knowledge by forming official ties with the International Council for Scientific and Technical Information (ICSTI). ICSU-WDS and ICSTI exchanged mutual Associate memberships in April 2014; establishing a formal relationship as the basis for active and productive collaboration.

DataCite

DataCite [WDS Partner Member] and ICSU-WDS signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) in October 2014 to consolidate their collaboration and increase the availability of high-quality scientific data to researchers worldwide. This MoU clearly states the intention of the two organizations to coordinate efforts in areas of mutual interest, such as data publishing and improving discoverability of trusted data services that support scientific research activities. To accomplish this, ICSU-WDS and DataCite will cooperate closely through joint WGs that will look to produce results beneficial to both their memberships. Furthermore, they will enhance strategic exchange and communication between these communities.

Federation for Earth Science Information Partners

ICSU-WDS held a Town Hall Meeting on 10 July 2014 at the Summer Meeting of the Federation for Earth Science Information Partners [WDS Partner Member] (ESIP) in Frisco, Colorado. Building on the fact that a number of WDS Members are active participants in the ESIP Federation, the WDS session not only gave current and prospective WDS Members an opportunity to find out more about ICSU-WDS and its present/planned initiatives, but also enabled them to explore synergies and establish mutually beneficial collaborations.

Administration & Governance

WDS Strategic Plan 2014–2018

2014 WDS Members' Forum

31st ICSU General Assembly

WDS Scientific Committee

WDS Members

WDS International Programme Office

Implementation Plan 2014–2015

The Implementation Plan complements the Strategic Plan 2014–2018. It is an evolving document continually reviewed and updated by the WDS Scientific Committee according to the achievements of ICSU-WDS and changes to the data stewardship and curation landscape. It is open for comments and [available online only](#).

WDS Strategic Plan 2014–2018

ICSU-WDS announced the publication of its first Strategic Plan in June 2014. The Plan, which covers the period 2014–2018, was produced by the WDS Scientific Committee (WDS-SC) over the course of its 9th and 10th face-to-face meetings in consultation with WDS Members. It outlines the following five major targets seen by the Scientific Committee as being important for ICSU-WDS to achieve the objectives defined in its Constitution:

1. Make trusted data services an integral part of international collaborative scientific research
2. Nurture active disciplinary and multidisciplinary scientific data services communities
3. Improve the funding environment
4. Improve the trust in and quality of open Scientific Data Services
5. Position ICSU-WDS as the premium global multidisciplinary network for quality-assessed scientific research data

The five-year Strategic Plan operates in unison with a rolling two-year Implementation Plan (initially for 2014–2015) that lists explicit activities towards achieving the identified targets. Unlike the more static Strategic Plan, the Implementation Plan is an evolving document that monitors the progress of the proposed activities and that can be updated by the WDS-SC as an activity is accomplished or its scope changes. Moreover, the Implementation Plan is an online resource that can be commented on directly by the WDS community such that its opinions and feedback can be heard and taken in consideration by the Scientific Committee as ICSU-WDS continues to further its mission.

2014 WDS Members' Forum

Over 70 people participated in WDS' biennial business meeting, the WDS Members' Forum, held on 2 November 2014 at the Jawaharlal Nehru University Convention Centre, New Delhi (the venue of SciDataCon 2014). The audience of this open event consisted of Representatives of many WDS Member Organizations, the WDS Scientific Committee (WDS-SC), as well those with an interest in ICSU-WDS.

Topics in the Scientific and Plenary Sessions included the WDS Strategic and Implementation Plans, as well as the progress and next stages of the WDS Knowledge Network and Data Publication Working Groups. Moreover, the Member Representatives in attendance supported a set of Bylaws for managing the daily affairs of ICSU-WDS, and also agreed that all Regular and Network Members should produce a public report of their activities every two years.

The WDS-SC was especially impressed with the highly relevant and interesting oral and poster presentations given by Representatives of WDS Regular and Network Members, and expressed its gratitude to the local participants and everyone else who attended the Forum.

31st ICSU General Assembly

Bernard Minster (Chair of the WDS Scientific Committee) and Mustapha Mokrane (WDS Executive Director) officially represented the World Data System at the 31st General Assembly of the International Council for Science (ICSU) held on 30 August–4 September in Auckland, New Zealand.

Professor Minster presented the Assembly Plenary with the WDS triennial report, which was well received. The Assembly resolved that WDS should continue with its mission, and thanked Japan for hosting and funding the International Programme Office.

A highlight of this meeting was the endorsement of a set of open access principles by the Assembly (see below). WDS Members contributed to these principles, which are of utmost importance to ICSU-WDS, since they will facilitate the process

of redefining and revising the WDS Data Policy by helping to clarify the legitimate restrictions to open access.

Other meetings at the General Assembly were also related to the open access issue, particularly in the context of scientific research data. At the ICSU National Members' and International Scientific Unions' fora, Dr Mokrane expressed the views of WDS on the subject of open access and on endorsing the principles. Additionally, an Open Data for Open Science event was organized by the United Kingdom Royal Society and the Committee on Data for Science and Technology (CODATA), and featured a keynote from Professor Geoffrey Boulton (elected CODATA President at its 2014 General Assembly), who coordinated the influential 'Science as an Open Enterprise' report.

Open Access and Misuse of Metrics

The ICSU General Assembly endorsed open access principles and provided key recommendations guarding against the misuse of metrics in the evaluation of research performance. In a strong show of support for open access to the scientific record, the Assembly – which unites representatives of 120 National Scientific Academies and 31 International Scientific Unions – voted for the [statement](#), which stakes out 5 key goals for open access and offers 12 recommendations that pave the road for attaining them.

WDS Scientific Committee

ICSU-WDS is governed by a Scientific Committee (the WDS-SC) composed of prominent scientists actively involved in Data/Computer Sciences, and dealing with large dataset issues and long-term data stewardship. The WDS-SC includes directors of WDS Member Organizations and covers a broad range of disciplines and geographical areas.

Chair

Jean-Bernard Minster: Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of California, United States of America (USA)

Vice-chairs

Michael Diepenbroek: Institute for Marine Environmental Sciences, University of Bremen, Germany

Françoise Genova: Centre de Données Astronomiques de Strasbourg, France

Members

Claudia Emerson: Sandra Rotman Centre, University Health Network / University of Toronto, Canada

Sandy Harrison: Centre for Past Climate Change, University of Reading, United Kingdom (UK) / Macquarie University, Australia

Wim Hugo: South African Earth Observation System, South Africa

Jane Hunter: School of Information Technology and Electrical Engineering, University of Queensland, Australia

Vasily Kopylov: All-Russian Research Institute of Hydrometeorological Information–World Data Centre, Russia

Guoqing Li: Centre for Earth Observation and Digital Earth, China

Ruth Neilan: Central Bureau of the International Global Navigation Satellite System Service, USA

Lesley Rickards: Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level, National Oceanography Centre, UK

Ryosuke Shibasaki: Center for Spatial Information Science, University of Tokyo, Japan

Ariel Troisi: Oceanography Department, Naval Hydrographic Office, Ministry of Defence, Argentina

Ex Officio Members

Orhan Altan: International Council for Science

Yasuhiro Murayama: National Institute of Information and Communications Technology, Japan

Sandra Harrison Appointed onto WDS-SC

On 1 May 2014, the WDS Scientific Committee and the IPO welcomed Sandra (Sandy) Harrison to ICSU-WDS. Sandy was invited by the ICSU Executive Board to serve on the SC following Kim Finney's retirement from in March 2014, and was a guest of the Chair at the 10th WDS-SC Meeting in Paris; proving her credentials as an excellent addition to the Committee.

WDS-SC Meetings in 2014–2015

The WDS-SC met on three occasions in 2014–2015. It convened for its 10th biannual Meeting on 31 March–2 April at the ICSU Secretariat in Paris, France. The Meeting predominantly focussed on finalizing the first WDS Strategic and Implementation Plans, with a view to formally publishing the documents. In addition, the WDS-SC re-examined the ‘full and open access’ concept in light of ICSU-WDS continuing to broaden its scientific coverage across diverse new domains.

The 11th Meeting of the WDS-SC took place on 6–7 November 2014, at the Jaypee Vasant Hotel in New Delhi. With the meeting immediately following the close of SciDataCon 2014, the SC discussed the outcomes of the conference and the necessary steps for SciDataCon 2016, before conferring on these with the Executive Committee of the Committee on Data for Science and Technology. The agenda also included an exploration of the current role of ICSU-WDS in Less Economically Developed Countries, and the means by which this might be strengthened in the future.

The Scientific Committee spent part of its 11th Meeting revising the WDS Data Policy based on the conclusions drawn on full and open access at its 10th Meeting and the subsequent open access statement endorsed by the International Council for Science (ICSU) General Assembly. This topic was returned to during the WDS-SC’s 12th face-to-face Meeting on 07–08 March 2015 at Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of California, San Diego; where the SC also examined its connection with WDS Network Members, as well as looking at the potential of setting up a WDS Working Group to develop a conceptual framework for indicator-based decision-making in the context of urban sustainability.

WDS Members

Member Organizations of ICSU-WDS from wide-ranging fields are the building blocks of a worldwide 'community of excellence' for scientific data. Not only do these Members participate in advancing WDS goals; their data holdings, services, and products are the cornerstone of the federated data system.

On 31 March 2015, ICSU-WDS had 89 Member Organizations in four different categories.

57 Regular Members: Organizations that are data stewards and/or data analysis services.

10 Network Members: Umbrella bodies representing groups of data stewardship organizations and/or data analysis services, some of which may or may not be WDS Regular Members. Usually serve as coordinating agents for nodes that have common characteristics and mostly common disciplines.

4 Partner Members: Organizations that are not data stewards or data analysis services, but that contribute support or funding to ICSU-WDS and/or WDS Members

18 Associate Members: Organizations that are interested in the WDS endeavour and participating in our discussions, but that do not contribute direct funding or other material support.

Member Organizations are formally accepted into ICSU-WDS by the WDS Scientific Committee, who safeguard the trustworthiness of ICSU-WDS by certifying Regular and Network Members according to internationally recognized standards (Partners and Associates are co-opted).

The following organizations were affiliated as WDS Members during fiscal year 2014.

Regular Members

Organization Name	Host Institution(s)	Country
Alaska Satellite Facility	Geophysical Institute, Fairbanks	United States of America (USA)
Canadian Astronomy Data Centre	National Research Council of Canada	Canada
Environment Climate Data Sweden	Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute	Kingdom of Sweden
Ocean Networks Canada	University of Victoria	Canada

Network Members

Organization Name	Host Institution(s)	Country of Secretariat
INTERMAGNET	British Geological Survey	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland (UK)

Partner Members

Organization Name	Host Institution(s)	Country of Secretariat
Federation of Earth Science Information Partners	Foundation for Earth Science	USA

Associate Members

Organization Name	Host Institution(s)	Country of Secretariat
ICSU Committee on Data for Science and Technology		French Republic
International Council for Scientific and Technical Information		French Republic
Research Data Alliance	European Commission / National Science Foundation + other United States agencies / Australian Government	UK

WDS International Programme Office

The WDS International Programme Office (WDS-IPO) coordinates the daily operations of ICSU-WDS and implements the decisions of the WDS Scientific Committee (WDS-SC). The IPO organizes the twice-yearly face-to-face meetings of the SC and the biennial WDS Conference, as well as conducting outreach and promotional activities.

Following an agreement with International Council for Science (ICSU), the WDS-IPO will be hosted and financially supported until 31 March 2016 by the National Institute of Information and Communications Technology (NICT) in Tokyo, Japan.

Financial Summary

The main source of income for financing the WDS-IPO and its activities comes from the contributions of NICT, its host organization. ICSU supports the costs incurred for one of the WDS-SC's biannual meetings, which is typically held at the ICSU Secretariat in Paris, France. This fiscal year, ICSU additionally supported WDS activities related to SciDataCon 2014. The accounts of the WDS-IPO are maintained and audited by NICT, its host institute. The statement of income and expenditure below is for the period 1 April 2014 to 31 March 2015; corresponding to the Japanese fiscal year 2014.

Statement of Income and Expenditure

Income	Japanese Yen
2014 Contribution from NICT	¥31,000,000
Total income	¥31,000,000
Expenditure	Japanese Yen
Communication and Promotion	¥12,924,009
Administrative Support	¥14,864,169
Travel and Meeting Costs	¥8,553,501
Other Costs (Insurance, Bank Charges, etc.)	¥967,243
Equipment	¥77,883
Total Expenditure	¥37,368,805
Net (Income - Expenditure)	-¥6,368,805¹

¹The negative balance has been compensated by NICT covering part/all of specific expenses incurred. The WDS-SC and IPO staff thanks NICT for its generosity in granting this additional contribution to the IPO funds.

Staff

Executive Director: Mustapha Mokrane

Senior Advisor: Takashi Watanabe

Programme Officer: Rorie Edmunds

Administrative Officer: Yuko Nikaido

The long-term ICSU vision is for a world where excellence in science is effectively translated into policy making and socio-economic development. In such a world, *universal and equitable access to scientific data and information is a reality and all countries have the scientific capacity to use these and to contribute to generating the new knowledge* that is necessary to establish their own development pathways in a sustainable manner.

WORLD DATA SYSTEM

IPO Host:

World Data System

International Programme Office (c/o NICT)

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ICSU

International Council for Science

